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The version of record

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ANNEX 1. QUESTIONNAIRE SENT TO THE EU AND LAC RESEARCHERS

ASSESSING THE QUALITY OF COLLABORATIONS BETWEEN EUROPEAN AND LATIN AMERICAN-CARIBBEAN RESEARCHERS IN THE FIELD OF HEALTH/PERSONALISED MEDICINE

Q1: Please select your gender

- Male
- Female

Q2: What is your nationality?

Q3: What is your current position? If you hold more than one position, select the one where you have a more stable position, and/or where you carry out most of your research work.

- PhD student
- Postdoc/research fellow
- Principal Investigator (PI)/Group leader
- Senior Group Leader,
- Clinician
- Healthcare professional
- Other (please specify)

Q4: In what type of research institution do you work? If you work in more than one institution, select the one where you carry out most of your research activities and/or have a more stable position.

- University
- Hospital
- Public research institute
- Private research institute
- Private company
- Non-Governmental Organization/foundation
- Other (please specify)

Q5: Country of the main research institution you work in.

Q6: Major field of research. Please select the one in which most of your research collaboration with EU/LAC is carried out.

- Infectious diseases
- Immune disease (including transplantation, autoimmune diseases)
- Cardiovascular disease (including hypertension)

- Diabetes (and other metabolic diseases)
- Cancer
- Neurological diseases
- Mental health disorders
- Other non-communicable diseases
- Rare genetic diseases
- Computational biology, modelling or imaging
- Artificial Intelligence
- Cellular biology, molecular biology
- Genomics, proteomics, genetics
- Pharmacology, pharmacogenomics
- Public health research, including epidemiology
- Preventive medicine
- Health economics
- Other (please specify)

Q7: Is personalised/precision medicine a research priority in your country? (e.g., research strategic agenda, policy or program in PM established)

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

Q8: Have you collaborated with European (if you are from LAC region) or LAC (if you are from Europe) research groups in the last 10 years in the field of PM?

- Yes
- No

Q9: If NO, could you please indicate if any of the following obstacles have impeded your participation in research activities in collaboration with European/LAC groups? More than one option is possible.

- Funding for collaborative research not available
- Funding timelines inadequate to conduct research
- Differences in ethical standards for scientific work (e.g., informed consent)
- Differences in enforcement of intellectual property rights
- Difficulties in sharing data/samples
- Lack /insufficient infrastructure
- Lack/insufficient expertise
- Lack of institutional support
- Insufficient time to collaborate in international projects
- My academic calendar is inconsistent with my collaborators
- General communication (language barriers, time zone differences)
- Cultural differences
- Separation from family and friends prevents international travel

- Getting visas for myself or collaborators
- Other (please specify)

Q10: How important is it for your success as a researcher, working in the field of biomedical research and PM, to collaborate with researchers from institutions located in Europe/LAC?

- 1) Don't know
- 2) Slightly important
- 3) Important
- 4) Very important
- 5) Extremely important

Q11: How much of your research work is done in collaboration with Europe/LAC?

- < 25%
- 25-50%
- 50-75%
- > 75%

Q12: With what type of partners from EU/LAC have you collaborated in the last 10 years? More than one option is possible.

- Scientists from other institutes/organisations
- Hospitals/healthcare professionals
- Newly established firms
- Non-start-up small- or medium-size firms
- Large firms
- Governmental bodies
- Non-profit, non-governmental organisations (NGOs)
- Consortium of private, public and scientific partners
- Research infrastructures
- Other (please specify)

Q13: Please select the type of research collaborations with European/LAC groups in which you have participated in the last 10 years. More than one option is possible.

- International research projects
- International Clinical research studies
- Training/capacity building activities: mobility programs, post doc stays, courses, short visits
- Institutional capacity building: Construction/enhancement of physical research infrastructures,
- Networking activities
- Non-formal collaborations (preparation of a scientific paper, sharing of research data, exchange of information)
- Other (please specify)

Q14: In which phase of the translational research continuum ** lie your main collaborations with Europe/LAC researchers? More than one option is possible.

- BASIC BIOMEDICAL RESEARCH: Research conducted to advance our understanding of a medical condition—but with no immediate application in health care. (i.e., GWAS studies; studies of cells, proteins, and DNA; studies on humans or existing datasets that focus on understanding biological, social and behavioural mechanisms that underlie health or disease
- APPLIED BIOMEDICAL RESEARCH. Research undertaken to gain new scientific and/or technical knowledge, but it is directed primarily towards a specific practical aim or objective. Includes: preclinical and animal studies
- TRANSLATION TO HUMANS: Seeks to move fundamental discovery into health application; provide clinical insights. Includes: Proof of Concept studies; phase 1 clinical trials; studies testing feasibility or safety of a new method of diagnosis, treatment, or prevention
- TRANSLATION TO PATIENTS: Health application to implications for evidence-based practice guidelines. Includes: Phase 2/3 clinical trials; studies to test efficacy of interventions in highly controlled settings
- TRANSLATION TO PRACTICE: Practice guidelines to health practices. Includes: Phase 4 clinical trials, comparative effectiveness research, community based participatory research, dissemination and implementation research, clinical outcomes research, health services research, meta-analyses/systematic reviews of interventions, development/implementation of guidelines
- TRANSLATION TO COMMUNITY: Health practice to population health impact, providing communities with the optimal intervention Includes: population-level outcomes research; wider implementation and dissemination; policy impacts; disease prevention through lifestyle/behaviour modifications; real-world health outcomes; true benefit to society
- Other (please specify)

Q15: Can you please indicate the European/LAC countries with which you have mostly collaborated in the last 10 years in Biomedical/PM research?

Q16: STRUCTURAL FACTORS in setting up and taking forward the research collaboration. What are the main factors that helped you to take part in collaborative research activities with Europe/LAC and what, in your opinion, is their significance to facilitating this collaboration.

	Not significant at all	Significant	Very significant	Don't know
Knowledge of collaborator's work/their knowledge of my work				
Previously worked with the collaborators				
Met at a conference/event				

Introduced through another researcher				
Facilitated by institution/funder/network				
Previously student/supervisor				
Other (please specify)				

Q17: How did you come into contact with the team(s) you are collaborating with? More than one option is possible.

- By chance, at a colloquium or lecture, or at a conference, because of a presentation, or because of working sessions or, on leave at another institution, to learn new skills, or catch up with the field
- By intention, by letter or phone call of solicitation
- By recommendation or referral by trusted colleagues
- Because it's a part of one's job – to mentor, to educate
- Other (please specify)

Q18: MOTIVATIONS in setting up the research collaboration. What have been the main motivations for participating in collaborative research with Europe/LAC in the last 10 years and their degree of relevance?

	Not relevant at all	Relevant	Very relevant	Don't know/Not applicable
To build or maintain links with researchers overseas				
To access expertise, interdisciplinarity and cross-fertilization of ideas				
To address an international research question				
To work with an existing contact				
To access specific skills or equipment				
To contribute with my specific expertise to an already existing collaboration				
To gain an international perspective on my research				
For my career development				

To provide support/mentorship to a junior researcher who is part of the collaboration				
To help build research capacity in another country				
To access funding sources				
To access data				
To collaborate with a business based overseas				
To find a research job out of your country				
Other (please specify)				

Q19: FUNDING FOR THE COLLABORATION. What types of funding sources have played a significant role in supporting your collaboration with Europe/LAC? More than one option is possible.

- Direct home public funding (national or regional)
- Home institution funding
- Home Charitable/philanthropic funding
- Home private sector/industry funding
- Overseas academic institution funding
- Direct overseas national government funding (national or regional)
- Overseas charitable/philanthropic funding
- Overseas private sector/industry funding
- EU research funding (ERC, H2020, HorizonEurope, other)
- Other Inter-governmental organizations (World Bank, WHO, PAHO, UNAIDS) Global health partnerships (Global Fund, GAVI, etc.)
- Other (please specify)

Q20: Can you please indicate the type of funding tools supporting the collaborations? More than one option is possible.

- Project-based funding (grants)
- Institutional funding (block funding, competitive funding, universities cooperation agreements)
- Industry funding (Contract agreements)
- Mixed models (research excellence initiatives)
- Mobility programs
- Other (please specify)

Q21: Can you please name the most important organisations that have funded your research collaborations in the last 10 years?

Q22: Does the funding that facilitated your research collaboration with EU/LAC come from an initiative focused on Personalised medicine or on general biomedical /health research?

- A programme/initiative focused on PM
- A programme/initiative focused on biomedical/health research
- Both of the above
- None of the above

Q23: GOALS, OUTCOMES AND BENEFITS OF THE BI-REGIONAL RESEARCH COLLABORATION. Please select the types of outputs from the collaborations. More than one option is possible.

- Jointly authored publications
- Grants awarded in collaboration with partner institute
- Undergraduate, PhD, master's degree
- Conference presentations in collaboration with partner institute
- Career benefits (promotions and employment opportunities)
- Personal financial rewards (financial compensation for individual researchers)
- Patents and other IPR
- Innovations: new products and/or services
- Other (please specify)

Q24: BARRIERS. Have you encountered any of the following barriers when participating in research collaborations with EU/LAC groups? Choose all that are relevant

- Academic Standards: Disparities in competitiveness, intensity of work, and general academic environments
- Funding timelines inadequate to conduct research
- Differences in ethical standards for scientific work (e.g., informed consent)
- Differences in enforcement of intellectual property rights
- Difficulties for sharing data/samples/biobanking
- Communication: Difficulty in communicating effectively via e-mail, phone, or video, language barriers and time zone differences
- Lack of opportunities, scientific activities (seminars or conferences) and invitations to present research at international platforms.
- Lack of institutional support or even opposition to participation in international collaborations by investigators or institutions
- Insufficient time to collaborate in international projects
- Lack of funding opportunities for research and collaboration
- Inconsistency in different academic calendars
- Cultural differences, perceived bias against or toward working with a specific region/country.
- Separation from family and friends prevents international travel

- Getting visas for myself or collaborators
- Other (please specify)

Q25: Do you collaborate with other regions in Health/Personalised Medicine research?

- Yes
- No

Q26: If answered YES, with which regions do you collaborate? More than one option is possible.

- North America
- Middle East and North Africa
- Sub-Saharan Africa
- Central and South Asia (Pakistan, India, Thailand, Indonesia, Singapore)
- East Asia (Japan, China)
- Pacific (Australia, New Zealand)

Q27: How would you rate the ease of collaborations with other regions in comparison to that with EU/LAC? Please further explain your choice.

- Easier
- The same
- More difficult

Q28: Do you have any suggestion/comment to improve the bi-regional collaborations between EU and LAC in health/personalised medicine research?

Q29: Please note that contact details will be archived securely and only used with your informed consent. Details of privacy policy are available at <https://www.eulac-permed.eu/index.php/privacy-policy/>

- Accept

** The following table tries to explain what each of these phases consists of and what their characteristics are. This information will be helpful to better understand and contextualise the answers provided by the researchers in our survey.

RESEARCH PHASE
Basic Biomedical Research: research conducted to advance our understanding of a medical condition—but with no immediate application in health care. (i.e., GWAS studies; studies of cells, proteins, and DNA; studies on humans or existing datasets that focus on understanding biological, social and behavioural mechanisms that underlie health or disease.
Applied biomedical research: research undertaken to gain new scientific and/or technical knowledge, but it is directed primarily towards a specific practical aim or objective. Includes: preclinical and animal studies;
Translation to humans: seeks to move fundamental discovery into health application; provide clinical insights. Includes: Proof of Concept studies; phase 1 clinical trials; studies testing feasibility or safety of a new method of diagnosis, treatment, or prevention.
Translation to patients: health application to implications for evidence-based practice guidelines. Includes: Phase 2/3 clinical trials; studies to test efficacy of interventions in highly controlled settings
Translation to practice: practice guidelines to health practices. Includes: Phase 4 clinical trials, comparative effectiveness research, community based participatory research, dissemination and implementation research, clinical outcomes research, health services research, meta-analyses/systematic reviews of interventions, development/implementation of guidelines
Translation to community: health practice to population health impact, providing communities with the optimal intervention Includes: population-level outcomes research; wider implementation and dissemination; policy impacts; disease prevention through lifestyle/behaviour modifications; real-world health outcomes; true benefit to society

Table 3. Different phases of the translational research continuum

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